

Development of high concentration hexavalent chromium resistant strain of *Aspergillus niger* for improved Cr⁶⁺ biosorption : Scanning Electron Microscopic and spectrophotometric studies

Subhabrata Guha Barman* and A. K. Banik

Biotechnology Division, Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Calcutta,
92, Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Kolkata-700 009, India

E-mail : sg_barman@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received 25 August 2009, accepted 14 January 2010

Abstract : Hexavalent chromium (Cr⁶⁺) is one of the most potent heavy metal pollutant released from various industries into water bodies. Most commonly used physico-chemical methods, for the removal of Cr⁶⁺ from waste waters are inefficient, expensive and also produces unmanageable toxic sludge. Recent studies showed that biosorption, based on metal-biomass interaction can be an alternative to commonly employed methods for Cr⁶⁺ removal from waste waters. Among the various biosorbent, bacteria, yeast, algae and fungi have potential for Cr⁶⁺ biosorption. In this study, *Bacillus circulans* MTCC 3161, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and *Aspergillus niger* were screened for high Cr⁶⁺ concentration tolerant strain isolation. It was found that, *Bacillus circulans* MTCC 3161 and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* are resistant up to 800 ppm of initial Cr⁶⁺ concentration present in the fermentation media, whereas, *Aspergillus niger* can resist up to 900 ppm of initial Cr⁶⁺ concentration. Moreover, it was also found that Cr⁶⁺ resistant *Aspergillus niger* have better biosorption potential (48% at 800 ppm) than that of Cr⁶⁺ resistant *Bacillus circulans* MTCC 3161 and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (40% and 38% respectively at 800 ppm). Scanning Electron Microscopic studies of mycelia with spores of parent cells of *Aspergillus niger*, Cr⁶⁺ resistant *Aspergillus niger* and Cr⁶⁺ loaded Cr⁶⁺ resistant *Aspergillus niger* revealed that exposure of parent *Aspergillus niger* to high Cr⁶⁺ concentration induces morphological changes. Moreover, Cr⁶⁺ loaded Cr⁶⁺ resistant *Aspergillus niger* shows further changes in mycelial and hyphal morphology which occurs may be due to biosorption of Cr⁶⁺ onto Cr⁶⁺ resistant *Aspergillus niger*. Metal-biomass interaction was confirmed by Fourier Transform Infra Red (FTIR) spectroscopic study which also indicates the presence of hydroxyl, amine, amide, carbonyl or carboxyl groups, on cell wall of *Aspergillus niger*.

Keywords : Hexavalent chromium, biosorption, *Aspergillus niger*, Scanning Electron Microscope, FTIR spectroscopy.

Introduction

With progress in technology, the natural environment often suffers from detrimental effects of industrial pollution. Heavy metals released by various industries are one of the major causes of aquatic pollution. Uncontrolled release of heavy metals has toxic, carcinogenic, mutagenic effects *in vivo*. Moreover non-destructiveness, bio-accumulation and subsequent magnification make them more potent pollutant. Generally they are deposited in liver, muscles, kidney, spleen, skin, bone and soft tissues of human beings¹.

A variety of physico-chemical methods, e.g. chemical precipitation, evaporation, coagulation, ion exchange, membrane filtration, electrolytic and adsorption techniques are commonly used for the removal of toxic heavy metals

from waste water. These methods were found to be either inefficient or expensive and may also be associated with the generation of unmanageable toxic sludge^{1,2}. In recent years, biosorption have gained much importance as an alternative eco-friendly, cost-effective method for heavy metal removal from industrial waste water. Biosorption is a process based on metal-biomass interaction. It is a metabolic independent process which can be performed by living and dead cells. Reusability of biomaterial, cost-effectiveness, efficiency in heavy metal removal and eco-friendliness makes the process more advantageous than the commonly employed physico-chemical methods²⁻⁴. Recently microbial systems like fungus^{16,17}, bacteria^{6,8-10}, yeast^{7,15} and algae^{11,12} have been used as biosorbent for heavy metal removal, as they can adapt quickly to

toxic concentrations of heavy metals and become metal resistant^{5,18,19}.

Pollution by chromium is of great concern as it is widely used in electroplating, leather tanning, metal finishing, stainless steel, textile and cement industry¹³⁻¹⁵. Though chromium is an essential nutrient in trace amount, it is an acute carcinogen above permissible limits. Chromium exists in several oxidation states, but more stable as Cr^{3+} and Cr^{6+} , while latter one is more toxic due to its high solubility in water. Due to toxic effects of chromium *in vivo*, stringent limits have been stipulated for the discharge of chromium into the environment. According to United States of American Environmental Protection Agency, the discharge of Cr^{6+} into water bodies is regulated to below 50 ppb while total chromium including Cr^{3+} , Cr^{6+} and its other forms are regulated to below 200 ppb^{13,20}.

Among the commonly used biosorbent, fungi are easy to grow and produce high yield of biomass and can be manipulated genetically and morphologically. Fungal organisms, more specifically *Aspergillus niger* are widely used in the production of gallic acid, citric acid and enzymes such as amylase, glucose isomerase etc. So this biosorbent is abundant and can be procured easily and cheaply^{20,21}.

The objective of this study is to isolate high Cr^{6+} concentration resistant *Aspergillus niger* strains, so that an alternative suitable biosorbent with high biosorption capacity can be developed. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) has high resolution to study the spatial relationship between cells and adsorbed metal. In addition, Fourier Transform Infra Red (FTIR) spectroscopy was used to determine the functional groups present on the surface of *Aspergillus niger*, which may be involved in Cr^{6+} biosorption.

Results and discussion

Screening of microorganisms for Cr^{6+} tolerance study : Effect of increasing concentration (ranging from 100 ppm to 1000 ppm) of Cr^{6+} in the fermentation media on *Bacillus circulans* MTCC 3161, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and *Aspergillus niger* is given in Figs. 1-3.

Isolation of Cr^{6+} resistant strain and their biosorption potency study : From the data obtained in the screening

Fig. 1. Cr^{6+} tolerance study of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*.

Fig. 2. Cr^{6+} tolerance study of *Bacillus circulans* MTCC 3161. (■) % of survival, (●) % of killing.

of microorganisms Cr^{6+} tolerance study, it was found that *Aspergillus niger* can resist up to maximally 900 ppm of Cr^{6+} concentration amended in the fermentation medium, whereas *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and *Bacillus circulans* MTCC 3161 can withstand up to 800 ppm of Cr^{6+} concentration. Using suitable fermentation media and proper Cr^{6+} concentration resistant colonies for each organism were isolated. Biosorption potency of resistant colonies were studied for the selection of suitable strain for Cr^{6+} removal.

Figs. 1-3 indicate the tolerance study of microorganisms. It is evident that, *Aspergillus niger* can resist higher concentration of Cr^{6+} (900 ppm) amended in the fermentation media, whereas *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and *Bacil-*

Fig. 3. Cr⁶⁺ tolerance study of *Aspergillus niger*. (■) % of survival, (▨) % of killing.

lus circulans MTCC 3161 can resist up to 800 ppm of Cr⁶⁺ concentration. At 800 ppm of Cr⁶⁺ concentration, amended in the fermentation media, Cr⁶⁺ resistant colonies of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* have the biosorption potency of 38%, whereas that of *Bacillus circulans* MTCC 3161 have 40%. But Cr⁶⁺ resistant colonies of *Aspergillus niger* have much higher % of biosorption potency

(48%). So *Aspergillus niger* not only can resist much higher Cr⁶⁺ concentration than *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and *Bacillus circulans* MTCC 3161, moreover Cr⁶⁺ resistant colonies of *Aspergillus niger* have much higher Cr⁶⁺ biosorption potency than the other Cr⁶⁺ resistant strains. So 900 ppm Cr⁶⁺ resistant *Aspergillus niger* can be used for further study as biosorbent of Cr⁶⁺.

From Fig. 4 it is evident that, at 900 ppm of initial Cr⁶⁺ concentration in the fermentation media during biosorption study of 800 ppm of Cr⁶⁺ resistant *Bacillus circulans* MTCC 3161 and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, shows considerable biosorption potency (34% and 30% respectively). On the contrary, at 1000 ppm of initial Cr⁶⁺ concentration in the fermentation media during biosorption study, 900 ppm of Cr⁶⁺ resistant *Aspergillus niger* shows biosorption potency (38%). This biosorption property may be due to the biosorption potency of the dead cells. Recent studies^{20,21} showed similar kind of results where dead fungal biomass (*Aspergillus niger*) could be used in the conversion of toxic Cr⁶⁺ into less toxic or non toxic Cr⁶⁺.

Scanning Electron Microscopic analysis : There are some reports²²⁻²⁴ that fungal morphology may change during the presence of some metal cations. Scanning Electron Microscopic (SEM) photomicrographs of the myce-

Fig. 4. Comparative Cr⁶⁺ biosorption study of different microorganisms (Cr⁶⁺ resistant).

lia with spore of Cr^{6+} unexposed *Aspergillus niger* was given in Fig. 5 and Cr^{6+} exposed *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀₀ were given in Fig. 6 (control, 900 ppm Cr^{6+} resistant), Fig. 7 (900 ppm Cr^{6+} resistant, fermentation media amended with 50 ppm Cr^{6+}) and Fig. 8 (900 ppm Cr^{6+} resistant, fermentation media amended with 80 ppm Cr^{6+}). The morphology was observed after growing fungus for 7 days at 30 °C with an initial pH 5.0 in the growth medium. Fig. 5 shows the hyphal morphological pattern of the parent *Aspergillus niger*. The hyphal morphological pattern of the 900 ppm Cr^{6+} resistant fungus grown in absence of Cr^{6+} was considered to be the control. *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀₀ grown in absence of Cr^{6+} have shown long, scarcely branched hyphae (Fig. 6) whereas

Aspergillus niger AB₁₀₀ grown in the medium containing 50 ppm Cr^{6+} have shown many bulbous cells, shorter length of mycelia, decreasing level of sporulation, higher level of branching (Fig. 7) than the control (Fig. 6) and parent *Aspergillus niger* (Fig. 5). These characteristics continuously increased (Fig. 8) when the fungus was grown in presence of higher concentration of Cr^{6+} (80 ppm). The surface of the mycelium became rough (Fig. 7) with Cr^{6+} exposed (50 ppm) fungus compared to the control and the roughness of the mycelium was further increased (Fig. 8) when the fungus was exposed with higher concentration of Cr^{6+} (80 ppm).

Fig. 5. Scanning Electron Micrograph of parent *Aspergillus niger*.

Fig. 6. Scanning Electron Micrograph of 900 ppm Cr^{6+} resistant *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀₀.

Fig. 7. Scanning Electron Micrograph of 900 ppm Cr^{6+} resistant *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀₀ after biosorption of 50 ppm Cr^{6+} , amended in the fermentation media.

Fig. 8. Scanning Electron Micrograph of 900 ppm Cr^{6+} resistant *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀₀ after biosorption of 80 ppm Cr^{6+} , amended in the fermentation media.

Researchers have reported similar type of observation regarding length of mycelium and level of branching. They found that the modification of the β -N-acetyl-D-glucosaminidase activity was associated with changes in hyphal morphological pattern, mainly concerning the degree of branching²⁵.

From the photomicrographs it can be stated that Cr^{6+} influenced the mycelial morphology of *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀₀. This might be due to some modification of the branching enzyme activity or other enzymes of the cell wall required for tip growth of mycelium. The other observation may also conclude the influence of Cr^{6+} on sporulation and integrity of the cell wall structure of the fungus.

FTIR analysis : In order to determine the main functional groups of Cr^{6+} resistant *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀₀ in Cr^{6+} biosorption, FTIR spectral study of 900 ppm Cr^{6+} concentration resistant *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀₀ cells and Cr^{6+} loaded (50 ppm and 80 ppm separately) resistant *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀₀ cells were performed.

Fig. 11 illustrates the FTIR spectrum of 900 ppm of Cr^{6+} resistant *Aspergillus niger* after biosorption of 50 ppm Cr^{6+} . FTIR spectral analysis of the finely powdered and dried biomass indicated broad peak at 3392.4 cm^{-1} indicate the stretching vibrations of -OH groups of the glucose and the -NH stretching of the protein and acetamido group of chitin fraction (a major cell wall component). The peak at 2928.8 cm^{-1} is due to the -CH stretching vibrations of -CH, -CH₂, -CH₃ groups. A moderate absorption band at 1639.5 cm^{-1} can be assigned to -C=O stretching vibrations of carboxyl groups or to the bending of amide groups (amide I band). Another moderately strong absorption band at 1410.4 cm^{-1} can be assigned to symmetrical stretching vibration of carbonyl groups. Absorption band at 1039.1 cm^{-1} can be attributed for the stretching vibrations of C-O, -C-OH groups. A broad peak at 583.1 cm^{-1} is due to stretching vibration of -SH group.

Fig. 9 and Fig. 10 depicts the FTIR spectrum of the 900 ppm Cr^{6+} resistant *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀₀ loaded

Fig. 9. FTIR spectrum of 50 ppm Cr^{6+} loaded 900 ppm Cr^{6+} resistant *Aspergillus niger* cells.

Fig. 10. FTIR spectrum of 80 ppm Cr⁶⁺ loaded 900 ppm Cr⁶⁺ resistant *Aspergillus niger* cells

Fig. 11. FTIR spectrum of 900 ppm Cr⁶⁺ resistant *Aspergillus niger* cells.

with 50 ppm and 80 ppm of Cr^{6+} . Here also due to stretching vibration of -OH group of glucose and stretching vibrations of -NH group of acetamido group exists, in both the cases, but in presence of high Cr^{6+} concentration, absorption band shifted towards lower wave number after biosorption of Cr^{6+} which indicates that at low initial Cr^{6+} concentration level, 900 ppm Cr^{6+} resistant *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀₀ have better potential for Cr^{6+} biosorption than at higher initial Cr^{6+} concentration. Since the intensity is a function of the changes in dipole moment and as well as the total number of functional groups present on the biosorbent surface, the significant intensity change was also observed for the absorption bands at 3392.4 cm^{-1} - 3398.7 cm^{-1} - 3410.6 cm^{-1} , 1639.5 cm^{-1} - 1653.8 cm^{-1} - 1649.5 cm^{-1} and 1039.1 cm^{-1} - 1072.9 cm^{-1} - 1073.8 cm^{-1} after biosorption when compared with control set. Moreover due to metal-biosorbent surface interaction a new band at 617.6 cm^{-1} appeared which also probably plays role in metal biosorption. Changes in band pattern that occurred may be due to exposure of the biosorbent surface to more toxic concentration of Cr^{6+} which leads to make the microorganism more potent to tolerate higher concentration of Cr^{6+} . In this regard it may be assumed that interaction of biosorbent surface with higher concentration of Cr^{6+} shifted the absorption band.

From these observation it may be assumed that, 900 ppm Cr^{6+} resistant *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀₀ strain amended with 50 ppm of initial Cr^{6+} concentration shows better biosorption capacity than the strain amended with 80 ppm of initial Cr^{6+} concentration.

Experimental

Microorganisms and culture conditions : Three different microorganisms were used in the present study and they were *Bacillus circulans* MTCC 3161, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and *Aspergillus niger*. *Bacillus circulans* MTCC 3161 was maintained by regular transfer to nutrient agar slant test tubes containing (g/L) Dextrose 10.0, Yeast Extract 2.0, Peptone 5.0, Beef Extract 1.0, Sodium Chloride 5.0 and Agar 40.0; pH was adjusted at 7.0 with 1(N) HCl or 1(N) NaOH. Slants were incubated at 37 °C for 48 h. *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* was maintained by regular transfer to Yeast Peptone Dextrose agar slant test tubes containing (g/L) Dextrose 10.0, Yeast Extract 5.0, Peptone 5.0 and Agar 40.0; pH was adjusted

at 5.0 with 1(N) HCl or 1(N) NaOH. Slants were incubated at 30 °C for 48 h. *Aspergillus niger* was maintained by regular transfer to Czapek Dox agar slant test tubes containing (g/L) Dextrose 30.0, Potassium di-hydrogen phosphate 1.0, Magnesium sulfate ($\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$) 0.5, Ferrous sulfate ($\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$) in trace amount and Agar 40.0; pH was adjusted at 4.8 with 1(N) HCl or 1(N) NaOH. Slants were incubated at 30 °C for 7 days.

Preparation of biosorbent : 10 ml of sterilized demineralized double distilled water was poured into each slant containing each of the microorganisms. Then using separate inoculation loop for different microorganisms, growth on the surface of different media containing agar slants were scraped off carefully. Each type of microorganism was harvested in separate sterilized cotton plugged conical flasks shaken properly in order to minimize clumping of microorganisms.

Screening of microorganisms for Cr^{6+} tolerance study : Before isolation of a suitable microbial strain for Cr^{6+} biosorption study, it is necessary to screen microorganisms under consideration for their Cr^{6+} tolerance, so that we can concentrate our study onto a specific microorganism. *Bacillus circulans* MTCC 3161, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and *Aspergillus niger* suspensions were prepared separately. 2 ml volume of each of the culture suspension with cell density of 1.6×10^7 cells/ml, 1.5×10^7 cells/ml and 2.1×10^7 cells/ml, respectively, were inoculated onto separate 100 ml conical flasks containing suitable fermentation broth. These medium were amended with Cr^{6+} in the form of potassium di-chromate solution. In this tolerance study, Cr^{6+} concentrations in the media was gradually increased from 100 ppm to 1000 ppm. A stock solution of Cr^{6+} in the form of potassium di-chromate ($\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$, AR grade) solution having 1000 ppm concentration was prepared and sterilized by autoclaving. Calculated volume of potassium di-chromate solution was added in the media to achieve the desired Cr^{6+} concentrations in the medium. Effect of increasing concentration of Cr^{6+} on different microorganisms under test, were understood by measuring the dry cell weight of the microorganisms. In each case microorganisms were separated from the broth by filtration using Whatmann filter paper. Biomass was dried in hot air oven for 3 h at 110 °C, to remove the total water content of the cell.

Isolation of Cr⁶⁺ resistant colonies of different microorganisms : From the Cr⁶⁺ tolerance study it was evident that microorganisms can resist different concentrations of Cr⁶⁺, which can be assumed by comparing the dry cell weight of the experiment of different microorganisms. Each microorganism was found to be resistant upto a certain concentration of Cr⁶⁺. Firstly each of the microorganisms was inoculated into corresponding fermentation broth media amended with maximum Cr⁶⁺ concentrations which they can resist. After proper incubation period, standard serial dilution and pour plate method was performed for each microorganism. After incubation period, larger identical colonies from each plate for each microorganism were isolated. They were transferred to suitable agar slant test tubes and after proper incubation period they were stored at 4 °C. Eight resistant colonies of *Bacillus circulans* MTCC 3161 were obtained at 800 ppm of Cr⁶⁺ concentration containing fermentation broth. In case of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* seven resistant colonies were obtained from 800 ppm of Cr⁶⁺ containing fermentation broth. Seven resistant colonies of *Aspergillus niger* were isolated from 900 ppm of Cr⁶⁺ containing fermentation media.

Comparative study of biosorption potency of isolated Cr⁶⁺ resistant strains : Each of the high Cr⁶⁺ concentration resistant colonies of each organism were tested for their biosorption potency study amended with increasing concentration of Cr⁶⁺, in the suitable fermentation broth. After proper incubation period, using the filtrate, after filtering off the biomass from the broth by Whatman filter paper, residual Cr⁶⁺ concentration in the filtrate was determined. Residual Cr⁶⁺ concentrations were determined by Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (Varian, Model number : AA240, GTA 120 fitted). From this residual Cr⁶⁺ concentration present in the filtrate, percentage of Cr⁶⁺ biosorbed can be calculated by :

Percentage of Cr⁶⁺ biosorption = $[(C_i - C_f)/C_i] \times 100$
 where C_i = initial Cr⁶⁺ concentration present in the fermentation media and C_f = residual Cr⁶⁺ concentration in the filtrate.

Scanning Electron Microscopic study of Cr⁶⁺ resistant *Aspergillus niger* : Czapek Dox broth media amended with 50 ppm and 80 ppm Cr⁶⁺ were separately inoculated with 900 ppm Cr⁶⁺ resistant *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀₀. After proper incubation mycelial mat were removed care-

fully from each set and standard dehydration process²² was followed. Dehydrated Cr⁶⁺ resistant and Cr⁶⁺ loaded Cr⁶⁺ resistant cells were attached to 10 mm metal mount using double site adhesive tape. Chamber pressure was maintained at 110 Pa which is generated by injecting the water vapor. Surface morphology of the samples were visualized by LED detectors of the FEI QUANTA Scanning Electron Microscope (Model number : 200MK2). SEM allowed the identification of any interesting structural change on the cell surface before and after Cr⁶⁺ biosorption.

Fourier Transform Infra Red (FTIR) spectroscopic studies of Cr⁶⁺ resistant *Aspergillus niger* : In order to determine the cell surface functional groups responsible for Cr⁶⁺ biosorption FTIR spectroscopy was carried out using a Perkin-Elmer RX I FTIR system (Model number : 54350). Czapek Dox broth media amended with 50 ppm and 80 ppm Cr⁶⁺ were separately inoculated with 900 ppm Cr⁶⁺ resistant *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀₀. After proper incubation mycelial mat were removed carefully from each set and samples were dried in hot air oven to remove the water vapor. Then dried cells were crushed into powdery form, using mortar-pestle and prepared for FTIR analysis as KBr mixed discs.

Conclusion : Biosorption is being demonstrated as useful alternative solution to conventional systems for cleaning the environment, contaminated by toxic metals. The development of biosorption processes requires further investigation in the direction of large scale set up to remove the toxic metals from industrial effluents after optimization of physical and chemical parameters. Current investigation was a lab scale development of high Cr⁶⁺ concentration resistant strains for removing more and more Cr⁶⁺ solution. Above results are encouraging to remove Cr⁶⁺ from aqueous media containing low level of Cr⁶⁺ (50 ppm) and whereas chemical treatment fails to remove residual Cr⁶⁺. To obtain a successful technological process the above work may be extended with actual industrial effluents.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. K. P. Dhara for providing FTIR facility. One of the authors (Subhabrata Guha Barman) is also grateful to University of Calcutta, for financial assistance and fellowship.

References

1. United States Environmental Protection Agency, Office of Research and Development, Washington, DC 20460; *In situ* treatment of soil and groundwater contaminated with chromium : Technical Resource Guide, 2000.
2. F. Vegilo and F. Beolchini, *Hydrometallurgy*, 1997, 44, 301.
3. H. K. Alluri, S. R. Ronda, V. S. Setalluri, J. S. Bondili, V. Suryanarayana and P. Venkateshwar, *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 2007, 6, 2924.
4. T. R. Muraleedharan, L. Iyenger and C. Venkobachar, *Current Science*, 1991, 61, 379.
5. T. Srinath, T. Verma, P. W. Ramteke and S. K. Garg, *Chemosphere*, 2002, 48, 427.
6. Y. B. Xu, H. H. Xiao and S. Y. Sun, *Journal of Zhejiang University Science Bulletin*, 2005, 6, 574.
7. G. W. Strandberg, S. E. Shumate and J. R. Parrott (Jr.), *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*, 1981, 41, 237.
8. H. Hussein, S. F. Ibrahim, K. Kandeel and H. Moawad, *Electronic Journal of Biotechnology*, 2004, 7, 30.
9. N. R. Horton, W. A. Apel, V. S. Thompson and P. P. Sheridan, *BMC Microbiology*, 2006, 6, 1.
10. J. H. Priester, S. G. Olson, S. M. Webb, M. P. Neu, L. E. Hermsan and P. A. Holden, *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*, 2006, 72, 1988.
11. T. A. Davis, B. Volesky and A. Mucci, *Water Research*, 2003, 37, 4311.
12. Z. R. Holan, B. Volesky and I. Prasetyo, *Biotechnology and Bioengineering*, 1993, 41, 819.
13. R. Aravindhana, B. Madhan, J. R. Rao, B. U. Nair and T. Ramasami, *Environmental Science and Technology*, 2004, 38, 300.
14. S. R. Popuri, A. Jammala, K. V. N. S. Reddy and K. Abburi, *Electronic Journal of Biotechnology*, 2007, 10, 358.
15. K. Parvathi and R. Nagendran, *World Journal of Microbial Biotechnology*, 2008, 24, 2865.
16. J. G. S. Mala, B. U. Nair and R. Puvankrishnan, *Journal of General Applied Microbiology*, 2006, 52, 179.
17. I. R. Acosta, X. Rodriguez, C. Gutierrez and M. de G. Moctezuma, *Bioinorganic Chemistry and Applications*, 2004, 2(1), 1.
18. S. Congeevaram, S. Dhanarani, J. Park, M. Dexlin and K. Thamaraiselvi, *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 2007, 146, 270.
19. I. Ahmed, M. I. Ansari and F. Aqil, *Indian Journal of Experimental Biology*, 2006, 44, 73.
20. D. Park, Y. S. Yun and J. M. Park, *Process Biochemistry*, 2005, 40, 2559.
21. D. Park, Y. S. Yun, J. H. Jo and J. M. Park, *Water Research*, 2005, 39, 533.
22. S. Srivastava and I. S. Thakur, *Current Microbiology*, 2006, 53, 232.
23. T. Akar, Z. Kaynak, S. Ulusoy, D. Yuvaci, G. Oszari and S. T. Akar, *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 2009, 163, 1134.
24. R. S. Bai and T. E. Abraham, *Water Research*, 2002, 36, 1224.
25. L. M. Pera, M. D. Baigori and D. Callieri, *Current Microbiology*, 1999, 39, 65.

